

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRESS AND PERSONALITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study examined the relationship between stress and personality among secondary school students. For the study of 200 secondary school students was selected by using random sampling techniques. The data was collected by using scale of Student's Stress Scale and Dimensional Personality Inventory Scale. Various statistical techniques like Mean, Standard deviation, t-test, Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation were used for analysis of data. In this endeavour the researcher found that 1) There was no significant difference in the level of stress among girls and boys of secondary school students. 2) There was no significant difference in the level of the various personality dimensions among girls and boys of secondary schools. 4) There was no significant difference in the level of personality among urban and rural, government and private secondary school students. 5) There was no significant difference in the level of stress among private and government, rural and urban secondary school students. 6) there was significant relationship between stress and personality among secondary school students.

Keywords:- Stress, Personality, secondary school students

1.1 Introduction

Stress is defined in terms of physical and physiological effects on a person and can be psychological as well as emotional too. The 21st century is called "the century of stress" because there is not a single person without stress. Stress is defined in terms of physical and physiological effects on a person and can be psychological as well as emotional too. In today's changing and competitive work environment stress level is increasing in both the students as well as the teachers. Stress is in everybody's life. There are many different types of stress that comes from many different sources and they all affect high school students. Students often go under serious amounts of stress trying to balance everything in their daily

lives. The term stress was also borrowed from the field of physics by one of the father of stress research Hans Selye. In physics, stress describes the force that produces strain on a physical body (i.e. bending a piece of metal until its shape occurs because of the force, or stress, exerted on it). The word 'stress' comes from the Latin 'stringere' to draw tight. It denotes force, strain or strong effort. In the physical world, stress means excessive force on an object, such as on a student. There is a difference between motivating pressure and destructive stress.

In the present study the researcher finds the relationship between stress and personality among secondary school students. No doubt stress is basically upon a person's psychological set up. It also in turn affects his or her physical and behavioral systems the sources of stress can be individual organizational and social. The term personality has been derived from the Latin word "persona" which was associated with Greek theatre in ancient times. "Persona" was the mask which the Greek actors commonly used to wear on their faces when they worked on the stage. Later on, it was used for the actor. According to the concept of mask, personality was thought to be the effect and influence which the individual wearing a mask left on the audience. Even today, for a layman, personality means the effect which an individual leaves on other people.

2.1 Review of Related Literature

Samantha et al. (2019) conducted a study on the level of stress experienced by senior high school students in Practical Research. Results revealed that there was no significant association of stress levels between gender and the skills and attitude of students.

Sagar et al. (2017) examined the level of academic stress among higher secondary school students. The study revealed that there was a significant difference between the academic stress of male and female participants, government aided & self finance school students and rural & urban area of higher secondary school students, but no significant difference was found among academic stress of arts, science and commerce stream students.

Subramani Chellamuthu et al. (2017) explored the academic stress and its relationship with mental health among high school students. The results revealed that students from private school experienced higher academic stress than that of government school students, and private school students have higher mental health status than their counterpart. It was also found that academic stress had a significant relationship with the mental health of high school students.

Deb et al. (2015) conducted a study on academic stress and mental health of Indian high school students and the associations between various psychosocial factors and academic stress. Nearly two-thirds (63.5%) of the students reported stress due to academic pressure – with no significant differences across gender, age, grade, and several other personal factors. About two-thirds (66%) of the students reported feeling pressure from their parents for better academic performance. About one-third (32.6%) of the students were symptomatic of psychiatric caseness and 81.6% reported examination-related anxiety.

Prabu (2015) examined the level of academic stress among higher secondary students. The male student's academic stress was higher than female students. The urban student's academic stress was higher than rural student. The Government school student's academic stress was less than private school student.

Suvarna (2015) conducted on Academic Achievement and Personality of 300 students of secondary schools of Mandya city. Result revealed that there was negligible positive relationship between Academic Achievement and Personality of Secondary School Students.

Wani Ahmad (2014) purpose of this study was to investigate the personality characteristics of higher secondary school students and to compare them on gender and locality. The results of the study revealed that the male higher secondary school students were found to be outgoing, more intelligent, assertive, venturesome, tender minded, suspicious, apprehensive, experimenting, self-sufficient, controlled and relaxed whereas female higher secondary school students were found to be reserved, emotionally stable, humble, shy, tough-minded, trusting, forthright, self-assured, conservative, group dependent, undisciplined and tense.

Rani Tripathi (2014) conducted on 120 students (60 boys 60 girls) studying in high schools selected purposively from Jalgaon district of Maharashtra state to study the achievement motivation and personality of high school students in relation to the type of urban and rural area. Results indicated that rural and urban area high school students differ significantly on Personality but gender wise and area wise students do not differ significantly on achievement motivation.

Hakimi et al. (2011) find out the relationships between personality traits and academic achievement among students. Participants were 285 students (191 female and 94 male). Results indicated there was no significant gender differences in the personality characteristics and academic achievement.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the difference in the level of Stress among girls and boys of secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.
- To determine the difference in the level of Personality among girls and boys of secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.
- To findout the difference in the level of Stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.
- To determine the difference in the level of Personality among students of rural and urban secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.
- To assess the difference in the level of Stress among students of govt and private secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.
- To findout the difference in the level of Personality among students of govt and private secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.
- To examine the relationship between Stress and Personality among students of secondary schools of Jalandhar Distt.

Hypotheses of the study

- There will be no significant difference in the level of stress among girls and boys of secondary schools.
- There will be no significant difference in the level of personality among girls and boys of secondary schools.
- There will be no significant difference in the level of stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools.
- There will be no significant difference in the personality among students of rural and urban secondary schools.
- There will be no significant difference in the level of stress among students of government and private secondary schools.
- There will be no significant difference in the level of personality among students of government and private secondary schools.
- There exit no significant relationship between stress and personality among students of secondary school.

3.1 Methods and Procedure

Sample Size

200 higher secondary school students were taken as a sample.

Tools

For collection of the data, Student's Stress scale developed by Dr.Zaki Akhtar (1938), personality scale developed by Dr. Mahesh bhargava was considered most appropriate tool by the investigator.

4.1 Results and Discussion

4.1 Table showing difference in the level of stress among girls and boys of secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know difference in the level of stress among girls and boys of secondary schools. After administering the scale, mean, S.D and t-value were computed and result have been presented in the table no. 4.1

Table no. 4.1

Gender	Mean	S.D.	N	D.F	T-value	Table value
Girls	183.86	23.64	100	198	0.075	1.96
Boys	177.83	26.27	100	198		

Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The t-value has been found to be 0.07 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus null hypothesis No.1 **“There is no significant difference in the level of Stress among girls and boys of secondary schools.”** is accepted. It indicates that there does not exist a significant difference in the level of stress among girls and boys students of secondary schools.

Figure No. 4.1 Showing average level of stress among girls and boys of secondary schools

Table no 4.1 showing the average level of stress among girls and boys of secondary schools belonging to girls is more than boys. This may be due to the fact that girls are sensitive and sincere by nature. Further girl students aspire more about their future rather than boys. This result of the present study is corroborated with the findings of the study conducted by **Kumari (2012)**.

4.2 Table showing difference in the level of personality among girls and boys of secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know difference in the level of personality among girls and boys of secondary schools. After administering the scale, mean, S.D and t-value were computed and result have been presented in the table no. 4.2

Table no. 4.2

Dimensional Personality Inventory	Group	Mean	S.D.	N	D.F	T-value	Table value
Activity-Passivity Trait	Girls	13.11	3.06	100	198	0.14	1.96
	Boys	13.77	3.02	100			
Enthusiastic and Non-Enthusiastic trait	Girls	13.9	3.22	100	198	0.55	1.96
	Boys	14.16	3.16	100			
Assertive-Submissive	Girls	12.48	2.98	100	198	0.001	1.96
	Boys	13.93	3.28	100			
Suspicious-Trusting	Girls	12.18	3.66	100	198	0.11	1.96
	Boys	12.89	3.99	100			
Depressive- Non Depressive	Girls	12.91	3.61	100	198	0.07	1.96
	Boys	13.9	3.02	100			
Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability	Girls	13.66	4.19	100	198	0.95	1.96
	Boys	13.63	3.99	100			

Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The t-value of first dimension of personality namely Activity-Passivity Trait of boys and girls, is 0.14 which is not significance at 0.05 level.

From the table 4.2 it is clear that t- value of Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait is 0.55, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

It is clear in the Table that t- value of personality dimension namely Assertive- Submissive trait is 0.001 respectively, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The t- value of Suspicious- Trusting trait is 0.11 which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance which again confirms that dimensions of personality have not influenced the gender of the students largely.

The above Table shows that the t- value of Depressive- Non Depressive trait has been found to be 0.07 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The t- value of Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability trait has been found to be 0.95 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Thus null hypothesis No. 2 “**There is no significant difference in the level of Personality among girls and boys of secondary schools**” is accepted. It indicates that there exist no significant difference in the various personality dimensions among girls and boys of secondary schools.

Figure No. 4.2 Showing average level of personality among girls and boys of secondary schools

Table no 4.2 showing the average level of personality among girls and boys of secondary schools. It is clear from the result that there is slight difference in the level of personality among girls and boys of secondary schools.

The mean value of Secondary School students (boys) on Activity-passivity Trait was 13.77, Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait was 14.16, Assertive- Submissive trait 13.93, Suspicious- Trusting trait 12.89 and Depressive - Non Depressive trait 13.9. It may be due to the fact that boys are given more freedom than girls in Indian society. So, they are more free and open to express their ideas, feelings, imaginations. They are ready for actions and independent judgement in comparison to girls. **Afrin (2019).**

The mean value of Secondary School students (girls) on Depressive- Non Depressive traitis 13.66. which is significantly higher than boys. It can be said that boys are more tender minded, sensitive, over-protected at upper primary stage whereas girls are more tough minded, self reliant and realistic thus non depressive too.

4.3 Table showing difference in the level of stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know difference in the level of stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools. After administering the scale, mean, S.D and t-value were computed and result have been presented in the table no. 4.3

Table no. 4.3

Area	Mean	S.D.	N	D.F	T-value	Table value
Urban	180.78	26.86	100	198		
Rural	180.05	23.88	100	198	0.82	1.96

Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The t-value has been found to be 0.82 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus null hypothesis No. 3 “**There is no significant difference in the level of Stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools.**” is accepted.

It indicates that there does not exist significant difference in the level of students of rural and urban secondary schools. It may be occurred due to the impact of modern educational technology and better educational facilities provided to both rural and urban students of secondary schools. So it is concluded that the level of stress among rural and urban students of secondary school does not differ significantly.

Figure No. 4.3 Showing average level of stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools

Table no 4.3 showing the average level of stress among students of rural and urban secondary schools. Depicts that urban students have more stress level than rural students. As urban school students are less engaged in extra indoor and outdoor activities rather than rural students. It may be occurred due the fact that the parents belonging to urban areas have high expectation from their children. The findings of **Sagar, et al. (2017)**. consolidate the result of present study.

4.4 Table showing difference in the level of personality among students of rural and urban secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know difference in the level of personality among secondary school students of rural and urban. After administering the scale, mean, S.D and t-value were computed and result have been presented in the table 4.4.

Table no. 4.4

Dimensional Personality Inventory	Group	Mean	S.D.	N	D.F	T-value	Table value
Activity-Passivity Trait	Rural	13.37	3.11	100	198	0.73	1.96
	Urban	13.51	3.00	100	198		
Enthusiastic and Non-Enthusiastic trait	Rural	14.36	2.70	100	198	0.14	1.96
	Urban	13.7	3.58	100	198		
Assertive-Submissive	Rural	13.02	3.08	100	198	0.42	1.96
	Urban	13.39	3.34	100	198		
Suspicious-Trusting	Rural	11.99	3.81	100	198	0.009	1.96
	Urban	13.08	3.41	100	198		
Depressive- Non Depressive	Rural	13.44	4.25	100	198	0.88	1.96
	Urban	13.37	3.52	100	198		
Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability	Rural	13.81	4.62	100	198	0.55	1.96
	Urban	13.48	3.48	100	198		

Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

From the table 4.4 it is clear that t- value of Activity-passivity Trait is 0.73, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The above Table shows that the t- value of Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait has been found to be 0.14 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

It is clear in the Table that t- value of personality dimension namely of Assertive- Submissive trait is 0.42 respectively, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The t-value of fourth dimension of personality namely Suspicious- Trusting Trait of boys and girls, is 0.009 which is not significance at 0.05 level.

The t- value of Depressive- Non Depressive trait which is 0.88 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance which again confirms that dimensions of personality have not influenced the gender of the students largely.

The t- value of Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability trait has been found to be 0.95 being not significant at 0.55 level of significance.

Thus null hypothesis No 4 “**There is no significant difference in the level of Personality among students of rural and urban secondary schools.**” is accepted. It indicates that there exist no significant difference in the personality dimensions among students of rural and urban secondary schools.

Figure No. 4.4 Showing average level of personality among students of rural and urban secondary schools

Table no. 4.4 showing the average level of personality among students of rural and urban secondary schools. It is clear from the result that there will be no significant difference in the level of personality among urban and rural students. The rural and urban students possess similar personality. This may be due to their present day exposure to several things and the support they get from the parents and community. This trend should continue forever. **Tok (2017)** also confirms the present derivation.

The mean value of Secondary School urbans students on Activity-passivity Trait was 13.51, Assertive- Submissive trait 13.39 and Suspicious- Trusting trait 13.08..This might be due to the greater willingness of urban students to disagree openly with their parents, a greater intensity of conflict and lower levels of cohesion with their parents and high levels of expectation. In rural areas, due to lack of well- organized and well- equipped schools, children remain below average in their general awareness and intelligence level.

The mean value of Secondary School rural students on Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait was 14.36, Depressive- Non Depressive trait is 13.44 and Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability trait 13.81.

4.5 Table showing difference in the level of stress among students of govt. and private secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know difference in the level of stress among students of govt. and private secondary schools. After administering the scale, mean, S.D and t-value were computed and result have been presented in the table no. 4.5.

Table no.4.5

Sector	Mean	S.D.	N	D.F	T-value	Table value
Private	173.76	24.47	100	198		
Govt.	187.93	23.83	100	198	0.0005	1.96

Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The t-value has been found to be 0.0005 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus null hypothesis No.5 “**There is no significant difference in the level of Stress among students of private and govt secondary schools.**” is accepted. It indicates that there does not exist significant difference in the level of stress among students of private and govt secondary schools. It may be due to the changing era of educational system conducting activities to enhance the self esteem and adapt stress management of students, through arranging and encouraging a variety of group activities, that ensuring all pupils experiences positive behaviour.

Figure No. 4.5 Showing average level of stress among students of private and govt secondary schools

Table no. 4.5 showing the average level of stress among government and private of secondary school students belonging to government is more than private. This result of mentioned study is consolidated by **Subhashini akurathi (2018)**. Who also concluded that government students are having high stressed than their private counterpart's.

4.6 Table showing difference in the level of personality among students of private and govt. secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know difference in the level of personality among students of private and govt. secondary schools. After administering the scale, mean, S.D and t-value were computed and result have been presented in the table no. 4.6

Table no. 4.6

Dimensional Personality Inventory	Group	Mean	S.D.	N	D.F	T-value	Table value
Activity-Passivity Trait	Govt	14.16	2.41	100	198	0.0006	1.96
	Private	12.72	3.44	100	198		
Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait	Govt	14.49	2.80	100	198	0.04	1.96
	Private	13.57	3.47	100	198		
Assertive- Submissive	Govt	13.71	3.17	100	198	0.02	1.96
	Private	12.7	3.19	100	198		
Suspicious- Trusting	Govt	13.33	3.09	100	198	0.0004	1.96
	Private	11.74	3.98	100	198		
Depressive- Non Depressive	Govt	14.44	3.63	100	198	0.0002	1.96
	Private	12.37	3.89	100	198		
Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability	Govt	15.03	3.39	100	198	1.14	1.96
	Private	12.26	4.25	100	198		

Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The t-value of first dimension of personality namely Activity-passivity Trait of boys and girls, is 0.0006 which is not significance at 0.05 level.

The t- value of Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait which is 0.04 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance which again confirms that dimensions of personality have not influenced the gender of the students largely.

The t- value of Assertive- Submissive trait has been found to be 0.02 being not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

From the table 4.6 it is clear that t- value of Suspicious- Trusting Trait is 0.00, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The above Table shows that the t- value of Depressive- Non Depressive trait has been found to be nil which not at all significant .

It is clear from the Table 4.6 that t- value of personality dimension namely of Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability is 1.14 respectively, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Thus null hypothesis No.6 **“There is no significant difference in the level of Personality among students of private and govt secondary schools.”** is accepted. It indicates that there exist no significant difference in the personality dimensions students of private and govt secondary schools.

Figure No. 4.6 Showing average level of personality among govt and private of secondary school students

Table no 4.6 showing the average level of personality among students of private and govt secondary schools. This result shows that there will be no significant difference in the level of personality among govt and private of secondary school students. The mean value of Secondary School government students on Activity-passivity Trait was 14.16, Enthusiastic

and Non- Enthusiastic trait was 14.49, Assertive- Submissive trait 13.71, Suspicious- Trusting trait 13.33, Depressive- Non Depressive trait 14.44 and Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability trait 15.03 which is significantly higher than private schools.

4.7 Table showing the relationship between stress and personality among students of secondary schools

The objective of the study was to know Relationship between stress and personality among students of secondary school. After administering the scale, mean and correlation were computed and result have been presented in the table no. 4.7

Table no. 4.7

Variable	Mean	N	D.F	R
Stress	181.48	200		
Activity-passivity Trait	13.44	200	398	0.31
Enthusiastic and Non- Enthusiastic trait	14.03	200	398	0.14
Assertive- Submissive	13.205	200	398	0.28
Suspicious- Trusting	12.535	200	398	0.20
Depressive- Non Depressive	13.405	200	398	0.35
Emotional Instability and Emotional Stability	13.645	200	398	0.36

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The r has been found to be 0.31 being significant at 0.05 level of significance. Thus null hypothesis No.7 “**There is no significant relationship between Stress and Personality among students of secondary school**” is rejected.

It indicates that there is a correlation between stress and personality among students of secondary schools which is significant. Thus there exists a slight positive correlation between stress and personality among students of secondary schools.

5.1 Conclusions & Suggestions

5.1 Conclusions

- There exists no significant difference in the level of stress and various personality dimensions among girls and boys of secondary schools.
- There exists no significant difference in the level of personality among urban and rural, government and private secondary school students.

- There exists no significant difference in the level of stress among private and government, rural and urban secondary school students.
- There exists significant relationship between stress and personality among secondary school students.

5.2 Suggestions

1. It is the suggestion that the sample size can be increased.
2. The sample area can be enlarged to other districts.
3. A co-relational study between stress and other variable such self-awareness, self-esteem, problem solving attitude etc., also can be done.
4. More studies can be conducted with different tools on the same problem.
5. This study was studied only the personality on secondary school students. It can be done on the other dimensions like comparison between stress of secondary school students.

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